

The Pre-Christian Libraries of the Middle-East: A Bibliographical History of Human Civilisation

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Abstract: *Preservation of facts relating to the long and arduous journey through civilisation and to give their experiences a permanence and communicate them asynchronously led human to erect libraries. Though the nature of the collection was more of an archival nature than what can be called a library proper in its earliest days, and books still lay long into the womb of future, the germination of the institution called library can be traced back to at least 23 centuries BCE. It was an age when the humans were mere a proto-writing race and used clay tablets as their writing surface. The ancient kingdom of Ebla in the south Syria and Nippur of the Southern Mesopotamia or modern Iraq were of the two earliest sites where world's first precursors of libraries were excavated. Interestingly, the modern library aspects such as collection development, organisation and management of holdings, use of bibliographic data, cataloguing etc. were also featuring in those early days, and exhibiting gradual maturity giving birth to other scholarly activities. Soon library became an insignia of cultural prestige. This article will trace this earliest development of libraries in the Middle East as a window to the history of the of human civilisation with special references to a number of world's oldest documentary collections viz. at Nippur, Hattusa, the Ashurbanipal's library at Nineveh and the great library of Alexandria*

Keywords: *Alexandrian library, Ashurbanipal, Book trade, Colophonology, Cuneiform tablets, Nippur-controversy, Papyrus scrolls.*

Introduction: Origin of libraries in the Middle East

Libraries were first developed in the scribal schools in Mesopotamia or today's Iraq, where they stored some literary and other texts for the purposes of training and practice the novices around the time when the human race was merely a proto-writing race (Robinson, 2009). Ancient libraries of the Middle East preserved collections written mostly on baked clay tablets or sometimes on waxed wooden boards and occasionally on papyri or leather in these languages like Sumerian, Akkadian, Hittite etc. using Cuneiform and rarely Hieroglyphic scripts (Pedersen, 1998). The Alexandrians used to write on papyrus with stylus in their Alphabetic Phoenician script derived from Hieroglyphics but also started using parchment towards the end of the 1st century BCE (MacLeod, 2004, p. 5) (Clayden, 2016).

Earliest instances of such collections can be dated back to 2600 BCE at some Sumerian city (Black,

2004, pp. 45-47) and also in Egypt around the same time (Ryholt, 2013, p. 25). But Black (2004, p. 47) writes that libraries in their more developed form as institutions housing reference collections of literary and scientific documents were fruits of the Babylonian and Assyrian civilisations flourishing in the Late Bronze Age (1500-1000 BCE) and Iron Age (1000 BCE onwards) of that region. The first individual to be named as a founder of a library was the great Assyrian King of the Middle Assyrian period called Tiglath-Pileser I (1115- 1077 BCE) who developed a large collection of cuneiform tablets in the library at the temple of their god Assur. But as the founder of the first systematic library of the ancient Middle East the neo-Assyrian king Ashurbanipal (668-627 BCE) has been named (Casson, 2002, p. 9).

Library vs archive controversy

Whether or not these ancient collections can be dubbed as libraries has been a staple controversy whenever such topics are discussed (Wellisch, 1981) (Robson, *Reading the Libraries of Assyria and Babylonia*, 2013). Both the terms have been used interchangeably and inconsistently, as Veenhof (1986, p. 4) suggests, but as often as not with a tendency to mark the difference between the two; *such as* an archive would be storing texts for official, administrative and documentation purposes, mainly in single copies, and the library would collect and preserve literary, religious, historical and scientific documents mainly for scholarship, often in multiple copies (Pedersen, 1998, pp. 1-12) (Pedersen, 1998, p. 280) (Robson, 2013). However, this distinction is often blurred (Black, 2004) and there are overlaps between the two concepts.

If the etymological connection of library with Latin *liber* or book is brought into the argument—that these ancient establishments did not have a single printed book, the same can be re-established as Eleanor Robson (2007, pp. 67-83) made a valid case for treating the cuneiform tablets of the first millennium BCE as ‘books’ under certain conditions. So, a library of ‘cuneiform books’, or later in time, of ‘papyrus books’ are not historically improbable.

No doubt, documents mainly served the purpose of administration and were chiefly accessible to the kings and state officials. But then, there were also evidences of tablets existing in multiple copies being used as scholarly references or lexicographical tools or text books of sort for the scribes and for instructional purposes. Towards the beginning of the Common Era such uses multiplied; in Egypt in particular, Alexandrian library’s role as a hub of scholarly and intellectual activities became phenomenal.

Both Veenhof (1986) and Pedersen (1998) suggest mix of archive and library documents in the collections, and Clayden (2016) quoting Eleanor Robson suggests parallel existence of the library and archive in single premises (at Nippur, but quite possibly everywhere else as well). Pedersen (1998, pp. 237-282) showed for the period 1500 to 300 BCE in particular, how in the Middle East collections had found stores in the setups like official buildings, temples and related structures, and private houses, and how a section of archives had their library divisions and vice versa. It is therefore often difficult to filter the pure library part from this mixed collections and purposes for discussion, if not impossible.

One thing should be remembered that today’s libraries in general, public or academic, or even special, follow a democratic philosophy, reflected in the first three of Ranganathan’s famous five laws. In spite of certain administrative restrictions occasionally imposed, the normal tendencies are to meet the users’ right to information and education and spread scholarship. This very characteristic was missing in the ancient libraries when ability to read and write had not become a public skill, nor had access to information become a public right. Most of the collections of the royal libraries were not publicly

accessible. Evidences of restrictions upon use of temple libraries excepting only competent ones can be found on the respective colophons (Black, 2004, p. 41).

Sites of ancient libraries

Excavations at various tells and mounds and other archaeological sites across the Middle East a fairly large number of documents were discovered at the royal palaces and temples—known as public buildings in the ancient Mesopotamia, and also at private houses chiefly of the scribal families and also of priests, musicians and exorcists, and sometimes at arsenals. Most of these excavated sites were distributed over the areas known as the ancient lands of the Hittite, Assyrian, Babylonian and Egyptian civilisations. Some of the important sites in the respective areas are mentioned below as examples:

- Hittite area: Ebla, Ugrait, Hattusas, Emar, Sarissa, Sapinuwa
- Babylonian area: Uruk, Nippur, Babylon
- Assyrian area: Assur, Kalhu, Dur sarrukin, Nineveh
- Egyptian area: Alexandria

Pedersen (1998, pp. 238-40) reports discoveries of at least 253 archives and libraries between 1500-300 BCE in 51 cities.

In this article we will limit our concentrations to the five important pre-Christian libraries. One is Tell Mardikh in modern Syria, which yields the most ancient clay tablets collection in the Middle East, and one from each of the 4 other ancient territories mentioned above, viz. Nippur near Tell Abu Salibhi in Iraq; Hattusa is modern Bogʻazköy in Turkey; Nineveh or Kuyunjik in Iraq and Alexandria in Egypt.

Ebla was once a part of the Hittite area but had belonged to a much older civilisation with tablets at its Royal Palace Area G dating back to 2300 BCE. Started in 1964 the Ebla campaign started producing significant results 1975 onwards (Matthiae, *Tell Mardikh: The archives and palace*, 1977) (Ebla digital archives home page) (Matthiae, 2021, p. 84).

The Mound V or the Tablet Hill at Nippur was excavated five times in all 23 seasons of excavations till 1985, started in 1889 by University of Pennsylvania under the direction of J.S. Peters. Pedersen did not categorise any of the collections from Nippur as a library or a library section attached to an archive. It is also famous for archaeologists' debate known as Nippur controversy whether the huge collections unearthed from the mound V were the part of a Temple Library at all (Hilprecht, 1903) (Peters, 1905) (Ahern, 2010) (Clayden, 2016). Still, Nippur has been included in the discussion as there have been ample evidences of scribal documents or literary pieces stored in some of those may-or-may not-be-called libraries. For example, a clay tablet now called the Farmer's Almanac, dating back to about 1500 BCE is believed to be a literary document used as a school primer containing instructions to a young farmer from his father on cultivation of barley with the help of irrigation (Renfrew, 1995, p. 193). The most important thing about the Nippur collection was that the precursor of the modern cataloguing practice was found in them. Two tablets dating to around 2000 BCE were identified listing 62 and 68 titles of the Sumerian works of literature respectively, of which 24 were titles of currently known literary works (Strout, 1956) (Casson, 2002).

Hattusa where excavation was started in 1906 by German scholar H Winckler and up to the 1990s was excavated in several spells.

Nineveh, famous for the Library of Ashurbanipal was excavated in several phases between 1842-1990 by the French, British, Iraqi and American excavators. The library was discovered by the British team led by A H Layard during the mid and late 19th Century.

The great library of Alexandria in Egypt has been added as an important site of Greek scholarship and culture surrogated in the Middle East.

The Range of Collection and Collection Development

Middle East libraries had holdings of some common types. A brief description of their variety follows. The Ebla Digital Archives [EbDA] records the latest total of 3182 tablets (Ebla digital archives home page, n.d.) which may still be classified into the same five broad categories as did Pettinato (1976) e.g. Economic-administrative; lexical; historical and juridical; Literary; Linguistic and philological texts.

Clayden (2016) classified the following types of tablets in Nippur archive as related to Accounting; Administrative; Legal; Lexical; Literary; Metrical; Monumental; Royal; School; Scientific; Mathematical; Incantation; and Prayer. Ashurbanipal's library at Nineveh comprises almost 30,000-32000 clay tablets and thousands of wooden boards (Casson, 2002) (Tulloch, 2021, p. 35) which include Omen Texts; ; religion and magic, dictionaries, official records, literary texts (Shah, 2021, p. 13). The holdings of the palace at Hattusa included literary texts; myths; legends; historical annals; state documents; treaties and instructions, omens and oracles; religious ceremonies; public occasions; rituals etc. (Pedersen, 1998, pp. 44-56) (Casson, 2002, p. 7). The collection of the library of Alexandria was *papyrus scrolls*, not clay tablets. It was the greatest and the largest of all ancient libraries known so far with 532,800 collections divided between two libraries—the main library with 490,000 collections and situated in the palace, and a smaller, daughter library having 42,800 scrolls, housed in a religious centre.

From which sources these ancient archives and libraries collected their holdings are not always known with certainty. But often they were the results of the copying practices of the scribal trainees. Beside that they used to keep abreast a varied range of administrative records, business transactions and communications, etc. and built collections of such documents for future use. Religious records, proverbs and omens also had a large share on the holding. Lexical documents, syllabaries, vocabularies formed another important category. Literary texts were the least in number.

Forceful acquisition and plundering were common. Apart from private sources, a portion of Ashurbanipal's collection was acquired by force from Babylonia after he killed his revolting half-brother Shamash-Shum-Ukin who ruled the city. Other means were by captivating scholars from Babylonia, acquisition from Tiglath-Pileser's library in Assur, inheritance from the library of king Sennacherib, and also by copying and composing (Casson, 2002, p. 11) (Robson, 2013, p. 42) (Black, 2004, p. 50). The Ptolemies of Alexandria used to send out agents to all corners of the Hellenistic territories to purchase copies of Papyri on all available subjects. They even seized books on ships at the Alexandria port for getting them copied for the Alexandrian library (MacLeod, 2004, pp. 4-5).

Management of the Collection

Evidences of careful and sophisticated collection management have been available from excavated sites and from textual references. Wooden shelving was common in Hattusa and Ebla (Veenhof, 1986) (Matthiae, 1977). In Ebla, relevant tablets were stored adjacent to the audience court of the palace for quick references (Wellisch, 1981) where some correlations were found between the shapes of the tablets and their contents such as round tablets were used particularly for economic and administrative

texts whereas square ones used freely. Round tablets were stored on the floor and square and rectangular ones on the shelves. This might be due to some purposeful, convenient ordering (Wellisch, 1981) or to prevent them from breaking by falling easily. Tablets were arranged on shelves slightly inclined to the wall, one upon another in a cascaded manner so that the first line of text on each tablet was visible over its preceding tablet. (Wellisch, 1981) (Matthiae, 2021, p. 89). In Nippur brick benches were used to store tablets leaning against each other like books (Veenhof, 1986). Wellisch (1981) has sensed some early examples of classificatory attempts in shelving similar tablets together in Ebla, and also in the listing of similar items together.

The Alexandria library had several wings and porticos lined with shelves along the covered walkways. Different sections were devoted to different classes of authors and different topics of learning (MacLeod, 2004, p. 4).

Ashurbanipal's library offered evidence of security management as the offenders were cautioned and warned with dire consequences in the name of Babylonian gods and goddesses against damages, improper handling, late return and theft of his collection (Casson, 2002, pp. 13-14).

Catalogue, Colophon and Bibliographical Records

The development of modern catalogue and cataloguing codes can be traced back to this period. Careful and systematic organisation of tablets lead us to the belief of a kind of catalogue in use at Nippur and other sites, supported by insufficient archaeological evidences (Strout, 1956). Nippur catalogue, however, was a very rudimentary type as they were mere listing of the titles, following no consistent order (Casson, 2002, p. 4). A more developed type was found in Hattusa dating to 1300 BCE recording detailed bibliographical entries by a number of fields (Casson, 2002, pp. 5-7).

Still, this catalogue was a limited tool as it listed only those works that a temple priest would need on various occasions, leaving out the other types of documents (Casson, 2002, p. 7). In the library of Alexandria cataloguing practices were also prominent. Callimachus prepared his *Pinakes* around 250 BCE listing some 120,000 scrolls of Greek poetry and prose, considered to be the first subject catalogue in the world, though they might serve as a bibliography of the Greek literature as well (Strout, 1956) (MacLeod, 2004, p. 5).

Another majorly important bibliographic practice developed in Hattusa was the use of *colophons*. The word was derived from Greek *kolophon* meaning the 'finishing touch'. Colophons were necessary information inscribed on the verso of a tablet after the main text has been finished. Casson (2002, p. 4) equated it to the modern use of *Title Page* of a book. Many of the tablets of Ashurbanipal's library had colophons which provide us among other things with information about the sources of the collection, their ownership, and the punishments for theft or damaging the tablets.

Scholarly Professions and Book Trade

The social impacts of libraries are quite well observed. The scribal art became a part and parcel of the library ecosystem from the early times, borne out by the existence of scribes' schools. Names of scribes Nabu-ah-iddina and his son Summa-balat of the Assyrian city of Assur are known today who had private libraries (Pedersen, 1998, p. 134). The chief scribe of Ashurbanipal's father and astrologer Balasi was appointed as Assurbanipal's tutor. The same practice of the librarian to act as the royal tutor was followed in Alexandria also (MacLeod, 2004, p. 4). The Ptolemies were themselves scholars and patronised scholars by offering them several benefits including exemption in taxes, making the

Alexandrian library as the pivotal place of scholarly activities. The first librarian of the library was Zenodotus (283-245 BCE). The second, Apollonius was the author of the epic *Argonautica*. It is under his tenure that Archimedes joined the scholarly circle and became a visitor of the library. The subsequent librarians were, as expected, high class scholars who attracted and encouraged scholars of other fields. Papyrus-book trade had already been established in Greek culture before the time of Aristotle. The Ptolemies, eager to acquire Greek collections in the Alexandrian library spent a lot from the exchequer. The production of books must also have encouraged the trade of papyrus produced in abundance by the river Nile.

Conclusions: A Bibliographical Window to the Human History

Studying the pre-Christian libraries of the Middle East, along with the archives, have been beneficial for Assyriological and Egyptological studies. The range of texts of these ancient libraries are rich sources of information to open up a bibliographical window to the history of peoples of more than two and a half millennia of a vast region. The catalogues and colophons too have been great aids for reconstructing the history. Colophonology has gained due importance in modern historical studies; for instance, the British Museum have undertaken studying the colophons under its *Ashurbanipal Library Project* to organise and read the texts to further research (Taylor, Jiménez, & Schnitzlein, 2023, p. 27). They also lend to the literary and biblical studies e.g. Ashurbanipal's library hosted the remarkable piece of literary text, the epic *Gilgamesh*; and the myth of *Atrahasis*, a Noah-like figure and the descriptions of a flood foreshadows the similar story in the Bible (Anderson, 2013, pp. 11-13). Each of the areas demand detailed and dedicated probes and would continue to add to our understanding of different aspects of human civilisations through the studies of one of the most ancient social institutions called library.

References:

- Ahern, J.-J. (2010, August). *Hermann Vollrat Hilprecht Papers*. Retrieved September 1, 2024, from University Archives and Record Center, University of Pennsylvania: <https://archives.upenn.edu/collections/finding-aid/upt50h655/#:~:text=Hilprecht's%20subsequent%20criticisms%20of%20other,issued%20a%20report%20exonerating%20Hilprecht.>
- Anderson, J. G. (2013). *Deep things out of darkness: A history of natural history*. Berkeley, California: University of California Press.
- Black, J. (2004). Lost libraries of ancient Mesopotamia. In J. Raven (Ed.), *Lost libraries: The destruction of great book collections since antiquity*. New York: Palgrave MacMillan.
- Casson, L. (2002). *Libraries in the Ancient World*. New Haven: Yale Nota Bene.
- Clayden, T. (2016). The Archaeology of the Nippur Archive. *al-Rāfidān: Journal of Western Asiatic Studies*, 37. Retrieved September 9, 2024, from <https://www.kokushikan.ac.jp/research/ICSAI/publication>
- Ebla digital archives home page*. (n.d.). Retrieved October 3, 2024, from Ebla digital archives: <http://ebda.cnr.it/index>
- Hilprecht, H. V. (1903). *Explorations in Bible Lands during the 19th Century*. Philadelphia: A. J.

- Holman and Company. Retrieved August 31, 2024, from <https://archive.org/details/cu31924019176217/page/n9/mode/2up>
- MacLeod, R. (2004). Introduction: Alexandria in history and myth. In R. MacLeod (Ed.), *The library of Alexandria: Centre of learning in the ancient world*. London: I.B.Tauris .
- Matthiae, P. (1977, July). Tell Mardikh: The archives and palace. *Archaeology*, 30(4), 244-253. Retrieved September 30, 2024, from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41706176>
- Matthiae, P. (2021). *Ebla: Archaeology and history*. London: Routledge.
- Pedersen, O. (1998). *Archives and libraries in the ancient near east:1500-300 BC*. Bethesda, Maryland: CDL Press.
- Peters, J. P. (1905). The Nippur Library. *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 26, 145-164. Retrieved September 2, 2024, from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/592887>
- Pettinato, G. (1976). The Royal Archives of Tell Mardikh-Ebla. *The Biblical Archaeologist*, 39(2), 44-52. Retrieved September 2, 2024, from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3209352>
- Renfrew, J. M. (1995). Vegetables in the ancient Near Eastern diet. In J. M. Sasson (Ed.), *Civilizations of the ancient Near East* (Vol. I). New York: Simon & Schuster Macmillan.
- Robinson, A. (2009). *Writing and script: A very short introduction*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Robson, E. (2007). The clay tablet book in Sumer, Assyria, and Babylonia. In S. Eliot, & J. Rose (Eds.), *A companion to the history of the book* (pp. 67-83). Malden, USA: Blackwell.
- Robson, E. (2013). Reading the Libraries of Assyria and Babylonia. In J. Koning, K. Oikonomopoulou, & G. Woolf, *Ancient Libraries*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ryholt, K. (2013). Libraries in ancient Egypt. In J. Konig, K. Oikonomopoulou, & G. Woolf (Eds.), *Ancient libraries*. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
- Shah, K. (2021). Who was Ashurbanipal. In A. Mardon, S. Sami, K. Shah, I. Fan, L. Orsini, K. Tulloch, . . . K. Maka, *The World's Oldest Library: The Library of Ashurbanipal*. Edmonton: Golden Meteorite Press. Retrieved September 1, 2024, from https://www.academia.edu/56399543/The_Worlds_Oldest_Library_The_Library_of_Ashurbanipal
- Strout, R. F. (1956, October). The Development of the Catalog and Cataloging Codes. *Library Quarterly*, 26(4). Retrieved from <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/10.1086/618341>
- Taylor, J., Jiménez, E., & Schnitzlein, B. (2023). The colophons of Ashurbanipal, king of the world. In G. A. Kiraz, & S. Schmidtke (Eds.), *Literary snippets*. New Jersey: Gorgias Press LLC.
- Tulloch, K. (2021). What was the library of Ashurbanipal. In A. Mardon, S. Sami, K. Shah, I. Fan, L. Orsini, K. Tulloch, . . . K. Maka, *The world's oldest library: The library of Ashurbanipal*. Edmonton: Golden Meteorite. Retrieved September 2024, 1, from https://www.academia.edu/56399543/The_Worlds_Oldest_Library_The_Library_of_Ashurbanipal

- Veenhof, K. R. (1986). Cuneiform archives, an introduction. In K. R. Veenhof (Ed.), *Cuneiform archives and libraries: Papers read at the 30e Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale, Leiden, 4-8 July 1983* (pp. 1-36). Leiden: Nederlands Historisch-Archaeologisch Instituut Te Istanbul. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from <https://www.nino-leiden.nl/publication/cuneiform-archives-and-libraries>
- Wellisch, H. H. (1981). Ebla: The world's oldest library. *The Journal of Library History (1974-1987)*, 16(3), 488-500. Retrieved September 26, 2024, from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25541212>